

ANNEX 4 IPCC Reference Approach for Estimating CO₂ Emissions from Fossil Fuel Combustion

It is possible to estimate carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from fossil fuel consumption using alternative methodologies and different data sources than those described in the Estimating Emissions from Fossil Fuel Combustion Annex. For example, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) reporting guidelines request that countries, in addition to their “bottom-up” sectoral methodology, complete a “top-down” Reference Approach for estimating CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion. Volume 2: Energy, Chapter 6: Reference Approach of the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories (IPCC 2006) states, “comparability between the sectoral and reference approaches continues to allow a country to produce a second independent estimate of CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion with limited additional effort and data requirements.” This reference method estimates fossil fuel consumption by adjusting national aggregate fuel production data for imports, exports, and stock changes rather than relying on end-user consumption surveys. The basic principle is that once carbon (C)-based fuels are brought into a national economy, they are either saved in some way (e.g., stored in products, kept in fuel stocks, or left unoxidized in ash) or combusted, and therefore the C in them is oxidized and released into the atmosphere. Accounting for actual consumption of fuels at the sectoral or sub-national level is not required. The following discussion provides the detailed calculations for estimating CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion from the United States using the IPCC-recommended Reference Approach.

Step 1: Collect and Assemble Data in Proper Format

To ensure the comparability of national inventories, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has recommended that countries report energy data using the International Energy Agency (IEA) reporting convention. National energy statistics were collected in physical units from several Energy Information Administration (EIA) documents in order to obtain the necessary data on production, imports, exports, and stock changes.

It was necessary to make a number of modifications to these data to generate more accurate apparent consumption estimates of these fuels. The first modification adjusts for consumption of fossil fuel feedstocks accounted for in the Industrial Processes and Product Use chapter, which include the following: unspecified coal for coal coke used in iron and steel production; natural gas, distillate fuel, and coal used in iron and steel production; natural gas used for ammonia production; petroleum coke used in the production of aluminum, ferroalloys, titanium dioxide, ammonia, and silicon carbide; and other oil and residual fuel oil used in the manufacture of C black. The second modification adjusts for the fact that EIA energy statistics include synthetic natural gas in coal and natural gas data. The third modification adjusts for the inclusion of ethanol in motor gasoline statistics. Ethanol is a biofuel, and net carbon fluxes from changes in biogenic carbon reservoirs in croplands are accounted for in the estimates for Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (see Chapter 6). The fourth modification adjusts for consumption of bunker fuels, which refer to quantities of fuels used for international transportation estimated separately from U.S. totals. The fifth modification consists of the addition of U.S. Territories data that are typically excluded from the national aggregate energy statistics. The territories include Puerto Rico, U.S. Virgin Islands, Guam, American Samoa, Wake Island, and U.S. Pacific Islands. These data, as well as the production, import, export, and stock change statistics, are presented in Table A-276.

The C content of fuel varies with the fuel's heat content. Therefore, for an accurate estimation of CO₂ emissions, fuel statistics were provided on an energy content basis (e.g., Btu or joules). Because detailed fuel production statistics are typically provided in physical units (as in Table A-276 for 2014), they were converted to units of energy before CO₂ emissions were calculated. Fuel statistics were converted to their energy equivalents by using conversion factors provided by EIA. These factors and their data sources are displayed in Table A-277. The resulting fuel type-specific energy data for 2014 are provided in Table A-278.

Step 2: Estimate Apparent Fuel Consumption

The next step of the IPCC Reference Approach is to estimate “apparent consumption” of fuels within the country. This requires a balance of primary fuels produced, plus imports, minus exports, and adjusting for stock changes. In this way, C enters an economy through energy production and imports (and decreases in fuel stocks) and is transferred out of the country through exports (and increases in fuel stocks). Thus, apparent consumption of primary fuels (including crude oil, natural gas liquids, anthracite, bituminous, subbituminous and lignite coal, and natural gas) can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Apparent Consumption} = \text{Production} + \text{Imports} - \text{Exports} - \text{Stock Change}$$

Flows of secondary fuels (e.g., gasoline, residual fuel, coke) should be added to primary apparent consumption. The production of secondary fuels, however, should be ignored in the calculations of apparent consumption since the C contained in these fuels is already accounted for in the supply of primary fuels from which they were derived (e.g., the estimate for apparent consumption of crude oil already contains the C from which gasoline would be refined). Flows of secondary fuels should therefore be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Secondary Consumption} = \text{Imports} - \text{Exports} - \text{Stock Change}$$

Note that this calculation can result in negative numbers for apparent consumption of secondary fuels. This result is perfectly acceptable since it merely indicates a net export or stock increase in the country of that fuel when domestic production is not considered.

Next, the apparent consumption and secondary consumption need to be adjusted for feedstock uses of fuels accounted for in the Industrial Processes and Product Use chapter, international bunker fuels, and U.S. territory fuel consumption. Bunker fuels and feedstocks accounted for in the Industrial Processes and Product Use chapter are subtracted from these estimates, while fuel consumption in U.S. Territories is added.

The IPCC Reference Approach calls for estimating apparent fuel consumption before converting to a common energy unit. However, certain primary fuels in the United States (e.g., natural gas and steam coal) have separate conversion factors for production, imports, exports, and stock changes. In these cases, it is not appropriate to multiply apparent consumption by a single conversion factor since each of its components has different heat contents. Therefore, United States fuel statistics were converted to their heat equivalents before estimating apparent consumption. Results are provided in Table A-277.

Step 3: Estimate Carbon Emissions

Once apparent consumption is estimated, the remaining calculations are similar to those for the “bottom-up” Sectoral Approach (see Estimating Emissions from Fossil Fuel Combustion Annex). Potential CO₂ emissions were estimated using fuel-specific C coefficients (see Table A-278).¹¹⁵ The C in products from non-energy uses of fossil fuels (e.g., plastics or asphalt) was then estimated and subtracted (see Table A-280). This step differs from the Sectoral Approach in that emissions from both fuel combustion and non-energy uses are accounted for in this approach. Finally, to obtain actual CO₂ emissions, net emissions were adjusted for any C that remained unoxidized as a result of incomplete combustion (e.g., C contained in ash or soot). The fraction oxidized was assumed to be 100 percent for petroleum, coal, and natural gas based on guidance in IPCC (2006) (see Estimating Emissions from Fossil Fuel Combustion Annex).

Step 4: Convert to CO₂ Emissions

Because the 2006 IPCC Guidelines recommend that countries report greenhouse gas emissions on a full molecular weight basis, the final step in estimating CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel consumption was converting from units of C to units of CO₂. Actual C emissions were multiplied by the molecular-to-atomic weight ratio of CO₂ to C (44/12) to obtain total CO₂ emitted from fossil fuel combustion in million metric tons (MMT). The results are contained in Table A-279.

Comparison Between Sectoral and Reference Approaches

These two alternative approaches can both produce reliable estimates that are comparable within a few percent. Note that the reference approach *includes* emissions from non-energy uses. Therefore, these totals should be compared to the aggregation of fuel use and emission totals from Emissions of CO₂ from Fossil Fuel Combustion and Carbon Emitted from Non-Energy Uses of Fossil Fuels Annexes. These two sections together are henceforth referred to as the Sectoral Approach. Other than this distinction, the major difference between methodologies employed by each approach lies in the energy data used to derive C emissions (i.e., the actual surveyed consumption for the Sectoral Approach versus apparent consumption derived for the Reference Approach). In theory, both approaches should yield identical results. In practice, however, slight discrepancies occur. An examination of past Common Reporting Format (CRF) table submissions during UNFCCC reviews has highlighted the need to further investigate these discrepancies. The investigation found that the most recent (two to three) inventory years tend to have larger differences in consumption and emissions estimates occurring earlier in the time series. This is a result of annual energy consumption data revisions in the EIA energy statistics, and the revisions have the greatest impact on the most recent few years of inventory estimates. As a result, the differences between the Sectoral and Reference Approach decrease and are resolved over time. For the United States, these differences are discussed below.

¹¹⁵ Carbon coefficients from EIA were used wherever possible. Because EIA did not provide coefficients for coal, the IPCC-recommended emission factors were used in the top-down calculations for these fuels. See notes in Table A-279 for more specific source information.

Differences in Total Amount of Energy Consumed

Table A-282 summarizes the differences between the Reference and Sectoral Approaches in estimating total energy consumption in the United States. Although theoretically the two methods should arrive at the same estimate for U.S. energy consumption, the Reference Approach provides an energy consumption total that is 2.5 percent lower than the Sectoral Approach for 2014. The greatest differences lie in lower estimates for coal and petroleum consumption for the Reference Approach (2.5 percent and 4.7 percent, respectively) and higher estimates for natural gas consumption for the Reference Approach (0.4 percent).

There are several potential sources for the discrepancies in consumption estimates:

- *Product Definitions.* The fuel categories in the Reference Approach are different from those used in the Sectoral Approach, particularly for petroleum. For example, the Reference Approach estimates apparent consumption for crude oil. Crude oil is not typically consumed directly, but refined into other products. As a result, the United States does not focus on estimating the energy content of the various grades of crude oil, but rather estimating the energy content of the various products resulting from crude oil refining. The United States does not believe that estimating apparent consumption for crude oil, and the resulting energy content of the crude oil, is the most reliable method for the United States to estimate its energy consumption. Other differences in product definitions include using sector-specific coal statistics in the Sectoral Approach (i.e., residential, commercial, industrial coking, industrial other, and transportation coal), while the Reference Approach characterizes coal by rank (i.e., anthracite, bituminous, etc.). Also, the liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) statistics used in the bottom-up calculations are actually a composite category composed of natural gas liquids (NGL) and LPG.
- *Heat Equivalents.* It can be difficult to obtain heat equivalents for certain fuel types, particularly for categories such as "crude oil" where the key statistics are derived from thousands of producers in the United States and abroad.
- *Possible inconsistencies in U.S. Energy Data.* The United States has not focused its energy data collection efforts on obtaining the type of aggregated information used in the Reference Approach. Rather, the United States believes that its emphasis on collection of detailed energy consumption data is a more accurate methodology for the United States to obtain reliable energy data. Therefore, top-down statistics used in the Reference Approach may not be as accurately collected as bottom-up statistics applied to the Sectoral Approach.
- *Balancing Item.* The Reference Approach uses *apparent* consumption estimates while the Sectoral Approach uses *reported* consumption estimates. While these numbers should be equal, there always seems to be a slight difference that is often accounted for in energy statistics as a "balancing item."

Differences in Estimated CO₂ Emissions

Given these differences in energy consumption data, the next step for each methodology involved estimating emissions of CO₂. Table A-283 summarizes the differences between the two methods in estimated C emissions.

As mentioned above, for 2014, the Reference Approach resulted in a 2.5 percent lower estimate of energy consumption in the United States than the Sectoral Approach. The resulting emissions estimate for the Reference Approach was 2.3 percent lower. Estimates of natural gas emissions from the Reference Approach are higher (0.4 percent), and coal and petroleum emission estimates are lower (2.6 percent and 3.9 percent, respectively) than the Sectoral Approach. Potential reasons for these differences may include:

- *Product Definitions.* Coal data is aggregated differently in each methodology, as noted above. The format used for the Sectoral Approach likely results in more accurate estimates than in the Reference Approach. Also, the Reference Approach relies on a "crude oil" category for determining petroleum-related emissions. Given the many sources of crude oil in the United States, it is not an easy matter to track potential differences in C content between many different sources of crude; particularly since information on the C content of crude oil is not regularly collected.
- *Carbon Coefficients.* The Reference Approach relies on several default C coefficients by rank provided by IPCC (2006), while the Sectoral Approach uses annually updated category-specific coefficients by sector that are likely to be more accurate. Also, as noted above, the C coefficient for crude oil is more uncertain than that for specific secondary petroleum products, given the many sources and grades of crude oil consumed in the United States.

Although the two approaches produce similar results, the United States believes that the "bottom-up" Sectoral Approach provides a more accurate assessment of CO₂ emissions at the fuel level. This improvement in accuracy is largely

a result of the data collection techniques used in the United States, where there has been more emphasis on obtaining the detailed products-based information used in the Sectoral Approach than obtaining the aggregated energy flow data used in the Reference Approach. The United States believes that it is valuable to understand both methods.

References

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Table A-276: 2014 U.S. Energy Statistics (Physical Units)

Fuel Category (Units)	Fuel Type	Production	Imports	Exports	Stock Change	Adjustment	Bunkers	U.S. Territories
Solid Fuels (Thousand Short Tons)	Anthracite Coal	1,638	[a]	[a]	[a]			
	Bituminous Coal	451,467	[a]	[a]	[a]			
	Sub-bituminous Coal	474,797	[a]	[a]	[a]	367		
	Lignite	72,147	[a]	[a]	[a]	4,440		
	Coke		76	946		(9)		
	Unspecified Coal		11,350	97,257		3,052	2,317	1,653
Gas Fuels (Million Cubic Feet)	Natural Gas	25,767,267	2,695,378	1,514,242	253,464	283,639		58,713
Liquid Fuels (Thousand Barrels)	Crude Oil	3,178,555	2,680,626	128,233	31,268			
	Nat Gas Liquids and Liquefied Refinery Gases	1,100,298	52,031	256,587	46,939			3,503
	Other Liquids	0	409,161	147,584	22,160			
	Motor Gasoline	(102,366)	17,987	161,225	(7,740)			34,763
	Aviation Gasoline		28	0	220			
	Kerosene		7	3,537	238			1,262
	Jet Fuel		34,479	59,464	1,091		169,671	9,731
	Distillate Fuel		71,050	401,875	8,743	397	6,240	12,856
	Residual Fuel		63,294	132,798	(4,482)	14,000	58,721	23,657
	Naphtha for petrochemical feedstocks		10,136	0	351			
	Petroleum Coke		2,088	197,491	(1,620)	8,331		
	Other Oil for petrochemical feedstocks		2,370	0	(624)	1,240		
	Special Naphthas		5,048	0	181			
	Lubricants		12,110	24,495	2,123			172
	Waxes		1,915	1,967	(134)			
	Asphalt/Road Oil		10,527	8,496	(581)			
	Still Gas		0	0	0			
Misc. Products			47	417	8			9,061

[a] Included in Unspecified Coal

Note: Parentheses indicate negative values.

Sources: Solid and Gas Fuels: EIA (2016); Liquid Fuels: EIA (1995-2015).

Table A-277: Conversion Factors to Energy Units (Heat Equivalents)

Fuel Category (Units)	Fuel Type	Production	Imports	Exports	Stock Change	Adjustment	Bunkers	U.S. Territories
Solid Fuels (Million Btu/Short Ton)	Anthracite Coal	22.57						
	Bituminous Coal	23.89						
	Sub-bituminous Coal	17.14				28.16		
	Lignite	12.87				12.87		
	Coke		21.86	25.41	21.86			
	Unspecified		25.00	25.97	20.86	266.92		25.14
Natural Gas (BTU/Cubic Foot)		1,032	1,025	1,009	1,032	1,031		1,032
Liquid Fuels (Million Btu/Barrel)	Crude Oil	5.80	6.04	5.80	5.80		5.80	5.80
	Nat Gas Liquids and Liquefied Refinery Gases	3.72	3.72	3.72	3.72		3.72	3.72
	Other Liquids	5.83	5.83	5.83	5.83		5.83	5.83
	Motor Gasoline	5.06	5.06	5.06	5.06		5.06	5.06
	Aviation Gasoline		5.05	5.05	5.05		5.05	5.05
	Kerosene		5.67	5.67	5.67		5.67	5.67
	Jet Fuel		5.67	5.67	5.67		5.81	5.67
	Distillate Fuel		5.83	5.83	5.83	5.83	5.83	5.83
	Residual Oil		6.29	6.29	6.29	6.29	6.29	6.29
	Naphtha for petrochemical feedstocks		5.25	5.25	5.25		5.25	5.25
	Petroleum Coke		6.02	6.02	6.02	6.02	6.02	6.02
	Other Oil for petrochemical feedstocks		5.83	5.83	5.83	5.83	5.83	5.83
	Special Naphthas		5.25	5.25	5.25		5.25	5.25
	Lubricants		6.07	6.07	6.07		6.07	6.07
	Waxes		5.54	5.54	5.54		5.54	5.54
	Asphalt/Road Oil		6.64	6.64	6.64		6.64	6.64
	Still Gas		6.00	6.00	6.00		6.00	6.00
Misc. Products		5.80	5.80	5.80		5.80	5.80	

Sources: Coal and lignite production: EIA (1992); Unspecified Solid Fuels, Coke, Natural Gas and Petroleum Products: EIA (1995-2015).

Table A-278: 2014 Apparent Consumption of Fossil Fuels (Tbtu)

Fuel Category	Fuel Type	Production	Imports	Exports	Stock Change	Adjustment	Bunkers	U.S. Territories	Apparent Consumption
Solid Fuels	Anthracite Coal	37.0							37.0
	Bituminous Coal	10,785.5							10,785.5
	Sub-bituminous Coal	8,138.0				10.3			8,127.7
	Lignite	928.2				57.1			871.1
	Coke		1.7	24.0	(0.2)				(22.2)
	Unspecified			283.7	2,526.0	63.7	618.6	41.6	(2,882.9)
Gas Fuels	Natural Gas	26,591.8	2,762.8	1,527.9	261.6	292.3		60.6	27,333.4
Liquid Fuels	Crude Oil	18,435.6	16,177.6	743.8	181.4				33,688.1
	Nat Gas Liquids and Liquefied Refinery Gases	4,096.4	193.7	955.3	174.8			13.0	3,173.1
	Other Liquids		2,383.4	859.7	129.1				1,394.6
	Motor Gasoline	(518.0)	91.0	815.8	(39.2)			175.9	(1,027.7)
	Aviation Gasoline		0.1	1.1	1.1				(2.1)
	Kerosene		0.0	20.1	1.3			7.2	(14.2)
	Jet Fuel		195.5	337.2	6.2			985.1	(1,077.7)
	Distillate Fuel		413.9	2,340.9	50.9	2.3	36.3	74.9	(1,941.8)
	Residual Oil		397.9	834.9	(28.2)	88.0	369.2	148.7	(717.3)
	Naphtha for petrochemical feedstocks		53.2		1.8				51.4
	Petroleum Coke		12.6	1,189.7	(9.8)	50.2			(1,217.5)
	Other Oil for petrochemical feedstocks		13.8		(3.6)	7.2			10.2
	Special Naphthas		26.5		0.9				25.5
	Lubricants		73.4	148.6	12.9			1.0	(86.9)
	Waxes		10.6	10.9	(0.7)				0.5
	Asphalt/Road Oil		69.9	56.4	(3.9)				17.3
Still Gas									
Misc. Products			0.3	2.4	0.0			52.5	50.3
Total		68,494.7	23,161.6	12,394.4	800.2	1,126.0	1,390.6	630.6	76,575.5

Notes: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding. Parentheses indicate negative values.

Table A-279: 2014 Potential CO₂ Emissions

Fuel Category	Fuel Type	Apparent Consumption (QBtu)	Carbon Coefficients (MMT Carbon/QBtu)	Potential Emissions (MMT CO ₂ Eq.)
Solid Fuels	Anthracite Coal	0.04	28.28	3.8
	Bituminous Coal	10.79	25.44	1,006.1
	Sub-bituminous Coal	8.13	26.50	789.8
	Lignite	0.87	26.65	85.1
	Coke	(0.02)	31.00	(2.5)
	Unspecified	(2.88)	25.34	(267.8)
Gas Fuels	Natural Gas	27.33	14.46	1,448.7
Liquid Fuels	Crude Oil	33.69	20.31	2,508.2
	Nat Gas Liquids and LRGs	3.17	16.89	196.5
	Other Liquids	1.39	20.31	103.8
	Motor Gasoline	(1.03)	19.46	(73.3)
	Aviation Gasoline	(0.00)	18.86	(0.1)
	Kerosene	(0.01)	19.96	(1.0)
	Jet Fuel	(1.08)	19.70	(77.8)
	Distillate Fuel	(1.94)	20.17	(143.6)
	Residual Oil	(0.72)	20.48	(53.9)
	Naphtha for petrochemical feedstocks	0.05	18.55	3.5
	Petroleum Coke	(1.22)	27.85	(124.3)
	Other Oil for petrochemical feedstocks	0.01	20.17	0.8
	Special Naphthas	0.03	19.74	1.8
	Lubricants	(0.09)	20.20	(6.4)
	Waxes	0.00	19.80	0.0
	Asphalt/Road Oil	0.02	20.55	1.3
	Still Gas	-	18.20	-
Misc. Products	0.05	20.31	3.7	
Total				5,402.4

Notes: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding. Parentheses indicate negative values.

Sources: C content coefficients by coal rank from USGS (1998) and SAIC (2004); Unspecified Solid Fuels, EIA (1995-2015), Natural Gas and Liquid Fuels: EPA (1995-2015).

Table A-280: 2014 Non-Energy Carbon Stored in Products

Fuel Type	Consumption for Non-Energy Use (Tbtu)	Carbon	Carbon	Fraction Sequestered	Carbon Stored (MMT CO ₂ Eq.)
		Coefficients (MMT Carbon/Qbtu)	Content (MMT Carbon)		
Coal	23.0	31.00	0.71	0.10	0.9
Natural Gas	305.1	14.46	4.41	0.65	10.6
Asphalt & Road Oil	792.6	20.55	16.29	1.00	59.5
LPG	2,109.4	17.06	35.99	0.65	86.4
Lubricants	281.1	20.20	5.68	0.09	1.9
Pentanes Plus	43.5	19.10	0.83	0.65	2.0
Petrochemical Feedstocks	[a]	[a]	[a]	[a]	37.7
Petroleum Coke	0.0	27.85	0.00	0.30	0.0
Special Naphtha	104.4	19.74	2.06	0.65	4.9
Waxes/Misc.	[a]	[a]	[a]	[a]	0.8
Misc. U.S. Territories Petroleum	[a]	[a]	[a]	[a]	0.4
Total					205.2

[a] Values for Misc. U.S. Territories Petroleum, Petrochemical Feedstocks and Waxes/Misc. are not shown because these categories are aggregates of numerous smaller components.

Note: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding.

Table A-281: 2014 Reference Approach CO₂ Emissions from Fossil Fuel Consumption (MMT CO₂ Eq. unless otherwise noted)

Fuel Category	Potential Emissions	Carbon Sequestered	Net Emissions	Fraction Oxidized	Total Emissions
Coal	1,614.5	0.9	1,613.6	100.0%	1,613.6
Petroleum	2,339.1	193.7	2,145.5	100.0%	2,145.5
Natural Gas	1,448.7	10.6	1,438.1	100.0%	1,438.1
Total	5,402.4	205.2	5,197.2		5,197.2

Note: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding.

Table A-282: Fuel Consumption in the United States by Estimating Approach (Tbtu)^a

Approach	1990	1995	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Sectoral	69,724	74,941	82,559	81,135	81,933	82,332	83,957	83,919	82,734	83,937	81,237	76,443	78,920	77,497	75,693	77,762	78,517
Coal	18,072	19,187	21,748	21,121	21,192	21,625	21,893	22,187	21,834	22,067	21,753	19,231	20,267	19,071	16,827	17,459	17,355
Natural Gas	19,184	22,170	23,392	22,466	23,163	22,561	22,623	22,282	21,960	23,371	23,594	23,193	24,312	24,679	25,832	26,560	27,232
Petroleum	32,468	33,585	37,418	37,548	37,578	38,145	39,441	39,449	38,940	38,498	35,891	34,019	34,342	33,747	33,034	33,743	33,931
Reference (Apparent)	68,730	74,018	81,524	80,676	81,431	81,724	83,600	83,495	82,061	83,899	80,398	76,464	77,829	76,499	75,299	76,005	76,576
Coal	17,573	18,567	20,957	20,710	20,797	21,081	21,735	21,986	21,534	21,577	21,391	19,243	19,620	18,756	16,483	16,948	16,916
Natural Gas	19,276	22,274	23,484	22,535	23,238	22,630	22,690	22,349	22,029	23,441	23,666	23,277	24,409	24,778	25,924	26,637	27,333
Petroleum	31,882	33,177	37,083	37,431	37,395	38,013	39,175	39,160	38,498	38,881	35,341	33,944	33,800	32,965	32,891	32,420	32,326
Difference	-1.4%	-1.2%	-1.3%	-0.6%	-0.6%	-0.7%	-0.4%	-0.5%	-0.8%	0.0%	-1.0%	0.0%	-1.4%	-1.3%	-0.5%	-2.3%	-2.5%
Coal	-2.8%	-3.2%	-3.6%	-1.9%	-1.9%	-2.5%	-0.7%	-0.9%	-1.4%	-2.2%	-1.7%	0.1%	-3.2%	-1.7%	-2.0%	-2.9%	-2.5%
Natural Gas	0.5%	0.5%	0.4%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%	0.3%	0.4%
Petroleum	-1.8%	-1.2%	-0.9%	-0.3%	-0.5%	-0.3%	-0.7%	-0.7%	-1.1%	1.0%	-1.5%	-0.2%	-1.6%	-2.3%	-0.4%	-3.9%	-4.7%

^a Includes U.S. Territories. Does not include international bunker fuels.

Note: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding.

Table A-283: CO₂ Emissions from Fossil Fuel Combustion by Estimating Approach (MMT CO₂ Eq.)^a

Approach	1990	1995	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Sectoral	4,858	5,169	5,734	5,657	5,697	5,750	5,857	5,886	5,800	5,876	5,692	5,299	5,472	5,336	5,130	5,279	5,322
Coal	1,719	1,823	2,071	2,011	2,022	2,066	2,093	2,121	2,083	2,106	2,076	1,835	1,935	1,820	1,607	1,667	1,656
Natural Gas	1,007	1,164	1,227	1,178	1,215	1,183	1,189	1,172	1,156	1,230	1,242	1,221	1,277	1,297	1,357	1,397	1,432
Petroleum	2,133	2,182	2,435	2,468	2,460	2,501	2,575	2,593	2,560	2,540	2,373	2,243	2,260	2,219	2,166	2,215	2,234
Reference (Apparent)	4,793	5,132	5,683	5,654	5,697	5,738	5,883	5,891	5,782	5,888	5,653	5,334	5,407	5,285	5,127	5,168	5,197
Coal	1,654	1,756	1,988	1,967	1,976	2,002	2,065	2,087	2,049	2,053	2,036	1,832	1,868	1,789	1,573	1,615	1,614
Natural Gas	1,013	1,170	1,233	1,182	1,220	1,188	1,194	1,176	1,160	1,235	1,247	1,226	1,283	1,303	1,363	1,401	1,438
Petroleum	2,126	2,206	2,462	2,505	2,501	2,548	2,625	2,627	2,573	2,600	2,370	2,276	2,256	2,193	2,190	2,152	2,145
Difference	-1.4%	-0.7%	-0.9%	-0.1%	0.0%	-0.2%	0.5%	0.1%	-0.3%	0.2%	-0.7%	0.6%	-1.2%	-1.0%	-0.1%	-2.1%	-2.3%
Coal	-3.8%	-3.7%	-4.0%	-2.2%	-2.3%	-3.1%	-1.3%	-1.6%	-1.7%	-2.5%	-1.9%	-0.2%	-3.4%	-1.8%	-2.1%	-3.1%	-2.6%
Natural Gas	0.6%	0.6%	0.5%	0.3%	0.4%	0.4%	0.4%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	0.4%	0.5%	0.5%	0.4%	0.3%	0.4%
Petroleum	-0.3%	1.1%	1.1%	1.5%	1.7%	1.9%	1.9%	1.3%	0.5%	2.4%	-0.1%	1.5%	-0.2%	-1.1%	1.1%	-2.9%	-3.9%

^a Includes U.S. Territories. Does not include international bunker fuels.

Note: Totals may not sum due to independent rounding.